

Supplementary Table 1 Completion rates (MDI or pump) by course type (N = 6586)*		
	Completed (n= 5940)	Did not complete (n=646)
	N (%)	N (%)
Standard DAFNE	3541 (94.7)	198 (5.3)
5x1 (F2F)	761 (85.2)	132 (14.8)
Remote DAFNE (fully remote)	1,383 (83.9)	266 (16.1)
Remote DAFNE (blended w/ F2F support)	21 (72.4)	8 (27.6)
Pump DAFNE (F2F)	154 (91.1)	15 (8.9)
Remote pump DAFNE (fully remote)	80 (74.8)	27 (25.2)

*163 people did not have the number of days of either a MDI or pump course recorded.

Chi2 P = 0.000